

Full Length Research Paper

Comparative Evaluation of Cefoxitin Liofilchem® Mic Etest Strips and Cefoxitin Disc for Detection of Methicillin Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* Isolated from Clinical Specimens in Federal Capital Territory, Nigeria

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This study evaluated the efficacy of Cefoxitin Liofilchem® MIC Test Strips and the disc diffusion test on methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA) isolated from hospital patients in Abuja, Nigeria from February to November 2015. Specimens were collected and identified by culturing on bacteriological media. *Staphylococcus aureus* isolated were confirmed for MRSA using oxacillin resistance screening agar base (ORSAB). Out of 48 MRSA isolated, 31.3% were isolated from urine specimens, 20.8% wound swabs, 14.6% Endo cervical swabs, 14.6% High vaginal swabs, 10.4% ear swab and 8.3% urethral swabs. The age range with the highest isolation rate is between 20-40 years while the lowest was from 40 and above. Antibiotics susceptibility testing of 48 identified Methicillin-Resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA) strains isolated from clinical samples in six-selected hospital in Federal Capital Territory (FCT) Abuja, Nigeria were tested for *in vitro* sensitivity to commonly used antibiotics using disk diffusion and Etest methods. High resistance was observed against cefoxitin (100%), oxacillin (100%), amoxicillin (87.5%), tetracycline (64.6%), erythromycin (56.3%), ceftazidime (56.3%), clindamycin (43.8%),

ciprofloxacin (27.1%), and linezolid (22.9%). The antibiotics susceptibility study showed that Vancomycin was the highest effective drug of choice (100%). A high percentage (34.2%) of the isolates was multidrug resistant while 65.8% of the isolates had MARI ≥ 0.4 . Out of 48 phenotypically identified MRSA isolates on agar disc diffusion method, further evaluation using MIC test strip showed that 62.5% (30) were susceptible to cefoxitin, while 37.5% (18) were resistant. All the isolates were resistant to more than five antibiotics tested; the MIC of these isolates to cefoxitin ranges from 6 - 64 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 0.38 - 2 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for vancomycin. Vancomycin MIC test strips were 100% susceptible. This study observed that MIC strip test is more accurate than agar disc diffusion method as 62.5% of the isolates that were resistant to cefoxitin on agar disc diffusion test were observed to be susceptible while 37.5% were resistant.

Keywords: *Staphylococcus aureus*, antibiotics resistance, MIC, hospital patients, Abuja

INTRODUCTION

The E-test is an impervious carrier with a continuous gradient of antimicrobial agent applied to one side of the strip. The test is performed in the same manner as the disc diffusion test but determines a minimal inhibitory concentration (MIC) of antimicrobial agent rather than a category result based on a zone size. Methicillin resistant

Staphylococcus aureus (MRSA) is any strain of *Staphylococcus aureus* that has developed genes encoding resistance to beta-lactam antibiotics, which include the penicillins (methicillin, dicloxacillin, nafcillin, oxacillin, etc.) and the cephalosporins.

In healthy people, MRSA carriage is associated with a

minor risk of developing an infection. However, when the integrity of the skin is broken, the risk of infection dramatically increases (Kluytmans, 2009).

The global misuse of antibiotics has facilitated the spread of resistant genes, resulting in multidrug resistant pathogen known as “superbug” In 2016, Center for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) reported that U.S. national data indicate that rates of infection are slowly decreasing but that the disease risk remains substantial, including an estimated 59,000 MRSA cases resulting in 9,670 deaths during CDC (2012) active bacterial core surveillance. Onanuga *et al.* (2006) in Abuja observed a prevalence rate of 40% among healthy women volunteers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. *Staphylococcus aureus* has developed resistance to a wide variety of antibiotics, which complicates the treatment of infections (Nwankwo and Nasiru, 2011).

The emergence of Methicillin Resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA) have been reported in several studies in Nigeria (Ikeh, 2003; Ghebremedhin *et al.*, 2009; Shittu *et al.*, 2011; Okon *et al.*, 2011). Hiramatsu *et al.* (2001) stated that methicillin-susceptible *S. aureus* (MSSA) become MRSA through the acquisition and insertion into their genomes of a large DNA fragment known as staphylococcal chromosome cassette mec (SCCmec), which contains the methicillin resistance determinant, *mecA* (Katayama *et al.*, 2000). Antibiotic susceptibility testing of *S. aureus* in Nigeria is based on phenotypic testing especially the disk diffusion technique but recent studies have relied on the PCR detection of the *mecA* gene for the identification and confirmation of MRSA, (Shittu and Lin, 2006, Okon *et al.*, 2009, Adesida *et al.*, 2005). In particular, methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA) has become a notorious etiologic agent for a wide variety of infections. It is one of the most important nosocomial pathogens worldwide (Claudia *et al.*, 2006 and Shittu *et al.*, 2009). The aim of this study was to compare the disc diffusion method with the Etest MICs testing for cefoxitin and vancomycin antibiotics used in developing and resource-poor country like Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

Ethical Clearance

Ethical clearance with assertion number FHREC/2014/01/65/05-11-14 was obtained from Health Research Ethics Committee of Federal Capital Territory, Health and Human Services Secretariat, Area 11, Garki Abuja.

Study area

This study was done in Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja. Abuja is the capital city of Nigeria. It is located in

the center of Nigeria, within the Federal Capital Territory (FCT). Abuja is known to be the best purpose-built city in Africa as well as being one of the wealthiest and most expensive. FCT was carved out of three states namely Niger, Kogi (formerly Kwara) and Nasarawa (formerly Plateau). The indigenous groups are Gbanyi, Koro, Gade, Egbura, Gwandara, Bassa and the Gana gana. There are six area councils in FCT and samples were collected from randomly selected hospital per area council namely Gwagwalada (University of Abuja Teaching Hospital), Bwari (Kubwa General Hospital), AMAC (Asokoro District Hospital), Kuje (Kuje General Hospital), Kwali (Kwali General Hospital), Abaji (Abaji General Hospital),

Sample collection

This prospective study was carried out from February to November 2015 in Federal Capital Territory (FCT) randomly selected hospitals. A total of 48 methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* isolated from non-repetitive skin and soft tissue specimens were used in the study. Qualified medical personnel collected these specimens from pus, wound sites, urethra, cervixes, vagina, and ear.

Isolation, Identification, and Biochemical Characterization of *Staphylococcus aureus*

The samples collected were cultured and screened for *S. aureus* on Mannitol salt agar (MSA) after 24 h incubation at 37°C and confirmed negative after 48 hours. Isolates that showed golden yellow coloration on MSA was further examined using colony morphological characteristics and biochemical properties (Gram stain reaction, catalase test, coagulase test, and Dnase) according to Cheesbrough, (2002).

Identification of Methicillin resistant *S. Aureus* (MRSA)

Oxacillin Resistance Screening Agar Base (ORSAB), supplemented with oxacillin (2g/L) was used to confirm isolates as methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. All isolates identified as *S. aureus* were streaked on ORSAB agar plate and incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours. After incubation, the plates were examined for growth. Blue-coloured colonies indicated presence of MRSA, while absence of growth was interpreted as Methicillin Sensitive *Staphylococcus aureus* (MSSA). The dual antibiotic supplement (oxacillin 1.0 µg, polymixin 25000 lu) and the presence of 5.5% NaCl have the potential to reduce the growth of non-Staphylococci organisms and select for the growth of MRSA.

Antibiotics susceptibility profile and multiple antibiotic resistance indexes

This test was conducted using ten (10) different antibiotics discs namely Ceftazidime-CAZ (30µg), Tetracycline-TE (30µg), Clindamycin-DA (2µg), Erythromycin-E (15µg), Ciprofloxacin-CIP(5µg), Oxacillin-OX (1µg), Cefoxitin-FOX (30µg), Amoxicillin-AML(30µg), Linezolid-LZD (30µg) and Vancomycin-VA (30µg) produced by Oxoid, England and following agar disc diffusion method modified by Kirby–bauer diffusion technique. The results were interpreted in accordance with the guidelines of the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI), 2016. MAR index = x/y, where x is the number of antibiotics resistant to and y is the number of antibiotics tested.

Phenotypic Detection of Methicillin Resistant *S. aureus* using E-TEST Strip for Cefoxitin and Vancomycin MIC

This study used Vancomycin and Cefoxitin Liofilchem® MIC Test Strip. These test strips are impregnated with a predetermined concentration gradient of antibiotics across 15 two-fold dilution of a conventional MIC method. Four morphologically similar colonies of *S. aureus* from an overnight culture on Mannitol salt agar were suspended in 5mL physiological saline. It was then compared to 0.5McFarland standard. A sterile swab was dipped in the broth culture and squeezed on the test tube to eliminate excess liquid. The swab was then spread evenly on Mueller Hilton agar (MHA). Cefoxitin MIC test strip and Cefoxitin disk were applied. This was also done for Vancomycin MIC test strip. According to the manufacturer protocol, reformed exponential gradient of antimicrobial agent is transferred into the agar matrix. These plates were incubated overnight at 35°C. The result of MIC was read at the point of completion inhibition of all growth including hazes, micro colonies, and isolated organisms. MIC break points for defining susceptibility categories as provided by CLSI (2016) interpretative values represented on (Table 1) were used to interpret the results.

Table 1. MIC test strip for antimicrobial susceptibility testing

Antibiotics	Abbreviation	Concentration in µg/ml	Reference
Cefoxitin	FOX	0.016-256	92066
Vancomycin	VA	0.016-256	92057

(CLSI, 2016)

RESULTS

The sample with the highest incidence of *S. aureus* was urine followed by wound; HVS and Ear while the least

were ECS and Urethral (Table 2). Among the area councils evaluated, Gwagwalada-UATH had the highest occurrence rate of *S. aureus*, while the least was Kuje (Table3). The highest isolate rate of MRSA was found in patients that were in the age range of 21-40 while the lowest was in the age range of 40 and above (Table 3). The antibiotics susceptibility study showed that Vancomycin was the highest effective drug of choice (100%) for the treatment of infections associated with *S. aureus* in Abuja, while high rate of resistance were observed for cefoxitin (100%), oxacillin (100%), Amoxicillin (87.5%), tetracycline (64.6%), erythromycin (56.3%), ceftazidime (56.3%), clindamycin 43.8%, ciprofloxacin (27.1%), linezolid (22.9%) (Figure 1). High percentages of the isolation had multiple antibiotic resistance indexes, greater or equal to four. MAR index = x/y, where x is the number of antibiotics resistant and y is the number of antibiotics tested.

Table 2. Frequency of isolation of MRSA in clinical samples

Clinical	No Sampled	No of MRSA	% MRSA
EAR	19	5	10.4
ECS	22	7	14.6
HVS	39	7	14.6
URETHRAL	17	4	8.3
URINE	63	15	31.3
WOUND	32	10	20.8

DISCUSSION

This study observed that the highest number of methicillin resistant *S. aureus* isolated was 20-29 from (17) age group followed by 30-39 (14). This is in agreement with the result of Odetoyin *et al.* (2015) who reported highest isolation of MRSA among 20-40 years of age in Ile-Ife, south Western Nigeria. The highest isolation rate was from urine (31.3%), wound swab (20.8%), endo-cervical swab (14.6%), and High vaginal swab (14.6%) Ear swab (10.4%), and urethral (8.3%) while the least was isolated from urine samples (30.2%) (Table 2). Significant percentage of the total *S. aureus* isolates evaluated 18(37.5%) harbored MRSA properties phenotypically and had MIC value ≥ 6 (Table 4). The MRSA isolates were (100%) resistant to cefoxitin and oxacillin (Figure 1). The isolates were also observed to be highly resistant to ceftazidime, tetracycline, amoxycillin and erythromycin; mildly resistant to clindamycin, ciprofloxacin but sensitive to linezolid and vancomycin (Figure 1). High percentages of the isolates were observed to express profile that is more resistant. All the MRSA isolates had MAR index ≥ 0.3 and showed resistance to more than three antibiotics tested (Table 5).

Out of 48 phenotypically identified MRSA isolates on agar disc diffusion method, further evaluation using MIC

Table 3. Distribution of MRSA among the age group

AGES	AMAC	BWARI	KUJE	KWALI	ABAJI	GWAS	TOTAL
< 10	3	1	1	1	0	3	9
19-Oct	0	0	2	1	1	0	4
20 – 29	2	2	1	4	6	2	17
30 – 39	3	5	1	1	0	4	14
40 – 49	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
50 – 59	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
60 – 69	0	0	0	0	0	2	2
Total	10	8	5	7	7	11	48

Figure 1. Antibiotics susceptibility profile of the MRSA isolates.

Table 4. Antibiotics resistance of MRSA isolates and MIC.

IC	NART	FOXMIC µg/ml	VAMIC µg/ml
ACWS	7	8	1.5
KWCUR	7	8	1
KWCHVS	6	8	1
KWCWS	7	6	0.5
GCWS	6	8	1.5
GCECS	7	64	2
GCES	7	34	0.5
GCUS	8	8	1.5
KJCWS (3 F)	6	8	1.5
GCUR	5	64	2
AMCUR (55 M)	6	24	1.5
BCWS (30 F)	5	8	1
AMCES	6	24	1.5
AMCUS	6	6	0.75
AMCECS	5	12	1.5
BCWS	6	24	1
BCUR	6	6	0.5
KJCUS	6	24	1

Keys: IC = isolates code, NART = number of antibiotics resistant to, MARI = multiple antibiotics resistance index, FOX=cefoxitin, VA=vancomycin, MIC = minimum inhibitory concentration in µg/ml, BCWS-Bwari Clinical Wound Swab, BCUR- Bwari Clinical Urine, GCES- Gwagwalada Clinical Ear Swab, GCUR-Gwagwalada Clinical Urine, GCECS-Gwagwalada Clinical Endocervical Swab. GCWS- Gwagwalada Clinical Wound Swab, GCES-Gwagwalada Clinical Ear Swab.

Table 5. Multiple antibiotics resistant index (MARI) of MRSA.

MARI	Number of occurrence	Percentage
0.1	0	0
0.2	0	0
0.3	0	0
0.4	8	16.7
0.5	10	20.8
0.6	19	39.6
0.7	10	20.8
0.8	1	2.1

Figure 2. Comparison of cefoxitin MIC strip calibrated in $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and cefoxitin disc

test strip showed that 62.5% (30) were susceptible to cefoxitin, while 37.5% (18) were resistant (Figure 2). This result is also in line with the finding of Raghavendra *et al.* (2017) who reported the MIC value of vancomycin for *S. aureus* ranged from 0.016 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ to one $\mu\text{g/mL}$. Singh *et al.* (2012) reported poor correlation between CLSI disc diffusion results of 49.5% and E-test MICs 82.0%, most notably for tetracycline, penicillin and ciprofloxacin. Previous studies with the Etest determined that results correlated well with the reference agar dilution method and that it is a useful guide for determining chemotherapy against many organisms. Further susceptibility study using vancomycin showed that the isolates were 100% susceptible to Vancomycin with MIC value ranging from 0.38 to 1.5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (Table 4). Goldstein *et al.* (2007) observed an excellent correlation between the E-test and the broth microdilution and agar dilution tests, suggesting that methods based on MICs, rather than disk diffusion methods, should be used to determine susceptibility to colistin. Tan and Ng (2006) found disk diffusion to be an unreliable method to measure susceptibility to colistin.

The presence of isolates with this resistant characteristic negate significant impact as MRSA has been reported to be endemic in many hospitals causing excess mortality and economic burden compared to methicillin-susceptible isolates (Cosgrove *et al.*, 2005; Adetayo *et al.*, 2014). MRSA strains have also been observed to show resistant to nearly all of the beta-lactam antibiotics by producing an alternative penicillin-binding protein known as PBP_{2a}. This protein is encoded by the *mecA* gene and has a low affinity to many beta-lactam antibiotics (Deurenberg *et al.*, 2007). MRSA strains are not only resistant to beta-lactams and cephalosporins, but also often show resistance to a wide range of antibiotic (Grundmann *et al.*, 2006).

Conclusion

The data obtained in this study suggest that MIC determination by Etest is an accurate alternative method for susceptibility testing of *S. aureus* with high sensitivity

and specificity than the disk diffusion technique. It is simple, consumes smaller amount of media and better confirmation using two methods for MRSA diagnosis.

Authors' Declaration

We declare that this study is an original research by our research team and we agree to publish it in the journal.

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